

Establishment of an open digital collection of historical music theory texts from German-speaking countries based on 19th-century examples (DigiMusTh)

Project Documentation and Guidelines

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Abstract

The DigiMusTh project focuses on the digital collection and analysis of historical music theory texts, with a particular emphasis on the 19th-century debate on major-minor dualism. While large digital collections of music theory texts already exist in other languages—such as the *Thesaurus Musicarum Latinarum* (TML) and the *Thesaurus Musicarum Italicarum* (TMI)—there is currently no comparable collection for German-language texts, despite their central role in European music theory since the 18th century. DigiMusTh aims to fill this gap by creating a sustainable and expandable digital edition that offers new perspectives for both musicology and the digital humanities.

A key aspect of the project is the integration of different types of texts. In addition to monographs and treatises, theoretical journal articles will also be included to provide a more comprehensive picture of the historical debate. Relevant periodicals, such as the *Neue Zeitschrift für Musik*, the *Allgemeine Musikzeitung*, and the *Neue Berliner Musikzeitung*, are already available in digital form. Since a complete collection is not feasible, a targeted selection will be made: only articles that are thematically linked to the existing corpus—either through shared authorship or direct references—will be included. This approach will offer a broader perspective on the discourse of the time and its dissemination in the public sphere.

Another goal is the technical and methodological advancement of digital music theory editing. The complex structure of the sources—including text, images, and musical elements—presents challenges that require innovative solutions. The continuous expansion of the collection will also contribute to the refinement of encoding guidelines and the development of music-theoretical ontologies. Additionally, the integration of individual research projects, such as master's theses or doctoral dissertations on relevant texts, is possible after review, allowing for a collaborative expansion of the collection.

In the long term, DigiMusTh aims to become an open, cooperatively expandable platform for historical music theory texts. Due to its interdisciplinary approach, the project is not only relevant to music theory and musicology but also to the digital humanities and the history of science, particularly concerning the physical and physiological foundations of harmonic theory. With its sustainable structure, DigiMusTh contributes to making historical music theory accessible and analyzable in modern digital formats.

Funded by [Text+](#), a consortium of the [National Research Data Infrastructure \(NFDI\)](#).

Proposed citation:

Moss, F. C., Roeder, T., Klinger, J., Keupp, C., & Roth, J. M. (2025). Establishment of an open digital collection of historical music theory texts from German-speaking countries based on 19th-century examples (DigiMusTh) – Project Documentation and Guidelines. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17974934>

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1 Introduction – digital editing of music-text documents

This report documents the rationale, workflow, and outputs of the scholarly research project *Establishment of an open digital collection of historical music theory texts from German-speaking countries based on 19th-century examples* (DigiMusTh) that involved the digital editing of combined music-text documents. Apart from being a documentation of the work accomplished within the project, this document is also meant to serve as guidelines for scholars with similar research interests. We thus adopt at times a writing style that directly addresses the reader in the second person, with the goal in mind to facilitate the adaptation of our workflow as much as possible.

The procedures described below should thus aid in helping scholars add further texts concerning the dualism debate to this collection. Moreover, it can also provide a scaffolding for a vast range of other research interests based on multimodal texts, and can thus be useful for a broad community within the digital humanities.

1.1 Project background

The DigiMusTh project ran from January to December 2025 at the Center for Philology and Digitality (Zentrum für Philologie und Digitalität, ZPD) of Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg (JMU), Germany. It was funded by Text+ (Kett et al., 2022),² a consortium within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur, NFDI; Kraft et al., 2021) as a so-called cooperation project within the Text+ Task Area “Collections”.

1.2 Project goal

The main goal of the project was to provide an open collection of music theory-related texts digitally encoded according to modern encoding standards, collated around the topic of the so-called “dualism debate”. The DigiMusTh project is thus a direct successor of the previous project *Digitizing the Dualism Debate* (DDD; Moss et al., 2021)³ that ran in 2021 as a collaboration between the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) and Université de Lausanne (UNIL) in 2021.

1.3 Accessing the project materials

During the year-long project duration, the team enhanced the texts taken from the DDD project and built a website displaying texts containing music notation, mathematical expressions, and diagrams. The texts are accessible with any web browser at the URL of the project website or via the “data” branch of the project GitHub repository.

- Project website: <https://fabianmoss.github.io/digimusth/>
- Project GitHub repository: <https://github.com/fabianmoss/digimusth/>

1.4 Project team

Prior to the project, Felicitas Stickler⁴ developed a first prototype of the website as part of her bachelor’s thesis for the Digital Humanities programme at JMU.⁵ The project team consisted of three research associates sharing a 65% part-time position: Corinna Keupp, Jana Klinger, and Torsten Roeder. They were supported by one student assistant with 7 hours per week, Janina-Marie Roth. Project leader Fabian C. Moss coordinated their efforts and steered the project.

² <https://text-plus.org/>

³ <https://dcmlab.github.io/ddd/>

⁴ <https://felicitasstickler.github.io/ba-thesis/>

⁵ <https://www.uni-wuerzburg.de/zpd/studium/bachelor/>

1.5 The texts

The project builds on the text collection provided by the DDD project, which had selected eleven texts, each of which constitutes an important contribution to the dualism debate. The following table gives an overview with the titles, authors, and years of publication of the texts. In the remainder of this documentation, we will frequently refer to the texts by their IDs stated in the last column.

No.	Title	Author	Year	ID
1	<i>Der accordliche Gegensatz und die Begründung der Scala</i>	Otto Kraushaar	1852	KRA1852
2	<i>Die Natur der Harmonik und der Metrik: Zur Theorie der Musik</i>	Moritz Hauptmann	1843	HAU1853
3	<i>Über die verschiedenen Bestimmungen der Tonverhältnisse und die Bedeutung des pythagoreischen oder reinen Quint-Systems für unsere heutige Musik</i>	Carl Ernst Naumann	1858	NAU1858
4	<i>Harmoniesystem</i>	Carl Friedrich Weitzmann	1860	WEI1860
5	<i>Die neue Harmonielehre im Streit mit der alten</i>	Carl Friedrich Weitzmann	1861	WEI1861
6	<i>Kritische Beleuchtung des C. F. Weitzmann'schen Harmoniesystems</i>	Franz Joseph Kunkel	1863	KUN1863
7	<i>Harmoniesystem in dualer Entwicklung</i>	Arthur von Öttingen	1866	OET1866
8	<i>Die beiden Tongeschlechter und die neuere musikalische Theorie</i>	Adolf Thürlings	1877	THU1877
9	<i>Die Lehre von den musikalischen Klängen: ein Beitrag zur ästhetischen Begründung der Harmonielehre</i>	Otakar Hostinský	1879	HOS1879
10	<i>Die Zukunft der Musiktheorie</i>	Georg Capellen	1905	CAP1905
11	<i>Das Problem des harmonischen Dualismus</i>	Hugo Riemann	1905	RIE1905

2 Workflow – preparing and transforming the data

This section specifies the different steps within the workflow of finding a relevant text for a collection, scanning it, transcribing it, developing a data model that fits the needs of the text and its intended presentation, transforming it to this data model, and enhancing the data with additional information or through the explicit modelling of formerly untranscribed parts of the text (such as mathematical expressions, music notation, or diagrams).

2.1 Finding and scanning texts

In the beginning of building a textual collection one has to select and find relevant texts. These texts can then be digitized by scanning the pages. If you are scanning the pages yourself you need to make sure that the quality of the scans adheres to typical standards. The German Research Community (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, DFG) published guidelines regulating the digitization of sources for humanities

research (Altenhöner, 2023). For information on technical standards for scanning texts refer to Section 3.2 of those guidelines.

If you have found a library or another institution that does the digitization for you, make sure they know about your/your field's technical requirements for the scans. If the text has already been scanned you need to find out whether these scans are free to use, or if a permission for usage in your project can be obtained from the rightholder.

If you are planning to add a text to our DigiMusTh text collection, a list of possibly interesting texts can be found here: <https://dcmlab.github.io/ddd/sources.html>.

2.2 Transcribing texts with OCR

Once you have scans of the selected texts, you need to transcribe them in order to make them computer-readable. There exist many tools that are able to do the bulk of the transcription process for you using automated procedures called Optical Character Recognition (OCR). OCR describes the process of automatically extracting textual information from visual input (e.g., scans) to a symbolic format (e.g., text). Depending on whether you need to transcribe hand-written or machine-written text some tools will work better than others. Mind that the used script (e.g. black letter vs roman) needs to be factored in.

The DDD project used Transkribus (Kahle et al., 2017)⁶ for OCR, but there are other possible choices of tools, such as eScriptorium (Kiessling et al., 2019),⁷ OCR4all (Reul et al., 2019)⁸ or LAREX (Reul et al., 2017),⁹ which all have different advantages and disadvantages. It is highly recommended to try out different softwares and models to find out which one works best for you and your source material.

To avoid too much manual work in later steps of the workflow, we recommend to mind a few caveats: Before transcribing the actual text, OCR software usually divides each individual page into a number of zones or regions (e.g. areas on the page that have text vs. areas that do not), a task that is commonly referred to as layout recognition. It has proven useful to supervise the automated process as it might be error-prone depending on the quality of the source scans. Moreover, it is beneficial to define and label a small set of different region types such as headings, paragraphs, footnotes, page numbers, music notation, graphics etc. For example, define a text-region in your OCR software called “heading” and use it to mark all headings.

Marking regions that do *not* contain text allows one to mark places on a page that contain a graphical/pictorial/non-textual element for later reference, while also making it clear for the OCR software that it does not need to attempt to transcribe this part of the page, thus reducing the overall error rate.

For each form of textual and non-textual phenomenon found in the texts there should be one and only one kind of zone. This is important, so that after exporting the transcription as XML the different types can be identified and handled differently without manually inspecting each instance and comparing it to the scans. Once the manual marking of the page areas is done, the transcription process can be conducted. Afterwards, the automated transcriptions should be corrected manually to fix (most) mistakes. When the quality of the text is satisfactory, they can be exported into the PAGE XML format that encodes the marked up page layout in a standardized manner.

2.3 Transforming export to TEI-XML

Such a PAGE XML export is not easily human-readable and should thus be further transformed using, for example, eXtensible Stylesheet Language Transformations (XSLT) or general-purpose programming languages such as Python. When applying data transformations, it is important to keep in mind that one should keep as much information as possible because one might not anticipate all possible use cases of

⁶ <https://www.transkribus.org/de>

⁷ <https://gitlab.com/scripta/escriptorium>

⁸ <https://www.ocr4all.org/>

⁹ <https://www.uni-wuerzburg.de/zpd/larex/>

one's own data. Others might be interested in aspects that one self would discard. This means concretely to keep all the information on the zones within the page that were defined earlier (coordinates, names, text zone or non-text zone and so on). Line beginnings and coordinates within larger zones might come in handy at a later point.

The *de facto* scholarly standard for digital text encodings is the XML-based format developed by the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI).¹⁰ We thus transformed the PAGE XML files (in our case provided by the DDD project) into valid TEI-XML files.¹¹ After transforming the PAGE XML to TEI, a central problem has to be tackled: When exporting a XML from an OCR software the typical structure is page-based, as the OCR transcription process is happening page by page. For the purposes of our text collection this page-based structure had to be changed to a structure that reflects the logical organization of the texts into sections, subsections, paragraphs, etc. This entails that paragraphs or footnotes spanning multiple pages have to be combined. Moreover, footnotes have to be attached to their position within the text so that they are coordinated in the absence of a page-based structure. Transforming the page-based structure into a content-based structure can be tricky, and we used a mix of XSLT-programming, regular expressions and manual adjustments for our project.

If you want to transform an XML-file with the goal of adding it to our text collection, you need to be able to validate the XML against the TEI all-schema. Beyond that, the better your data model fits ours, the better displaying your text on our website will work (e.g. display of music examples, graphics, mathematical expressions). For a list of all the used elements and their meaning see the table in the following chapter.

2.4 Data Model

All texts in our collection are encoded in TEI-XML. The data model follows the logical structure of the text instead of the structure of the individual pages, and the general structure of the documents is typical for TEI-XML:

1. Within the `<TEI>` root element the `<teiHeader>` with all the metadata on the text and its encoding can be found.
2. Following the `<teiHeader>` comes a section with a number of `<facsimile>` elements which contain information on the individual pages the text was transcribed from. For each scanned page there is a `<facsimile>` element with a unique `@xml:id`. It further contains a `<surface>`-element that is in turn comprised of a `<graphic>` element that links to the image of the scanned page as well as a number of `<zone>` elements, each one defining the area on the linked image in which different types of text or non-text are located. The `@points` within `<zone>` defines the area on the linked image and the `@rendition` defines whether the zone contains a text region, music notation or graphic. In `@subtype` all text regions are further defined as paragraphs, headings, lists, or footnotes.
3. After the `<facsimile>` elements comes the `<text>` element in which the actual transcribed and encoded text is placed. Here, the title pages, table of contents and preface can be found in the `<front>`, followed by the main content of each text in the `<body>` and possibly by a postface in the `<back>`.

The rest of the elements and attributes used in the collection are summarized in the table below, along with examples and comments on specific use cases.

¹⁰ <https://tei-c.org/>

¹¹ The transformed TEI-XML files from the DDD project might be a useful example to orient yourself towards. They can be found in [the projects GitHub repository](#). There navigate to /data. In there you find a folder for each text (e.g. CAP1905). In each of these folders you can find a .xml-file with '_tei' in the file name. If you want to use these files as orientation, also refer to the Data Model-chapter of this text.

Use case	Tag	Example	Comment
title page	<titlePage>		Title pages were encoded following the rules of the DTABf. Their guidelines can be found here: https://www.deutschestextarchiv.de/doku/basisformat/tbAllg.html
chapters	<div>	<div type="chapter" n="1">	The @n attribute refers to the level of a chapter, e.g. n="1" for a first-level chapter, whereas subchapters would have n="2" etc.
headings	<head>	<head facs="#zone-id"> Heading </head>	The <head> element always immediately follows the div@type="chapter". The @facs contains a link to the <zone> of the corresponding text on the scanned page.
line beginning	<lb/>	<lb facs="#zone-id" n="001" />	This empty element marks the beginning of a new line. @n contains the line number on the page.
page beginning	<pb>	<pb facs="#facs_13" n="9"/>	This empty element marks the beginning of a new page. @n contains the page number. If there is no page number printed on the page, then @n remains empty.
hyphens	<pc>	vor<pc>-</pc><lb/>geführt	Hyphens at the end of a line, linking two parts of the same word, are marked with the <pc> (punctuation character) element and enable the display of the text in forms independent from the original line breaks.
paragraphs	<p>	<p facs="#zone-id"> text text text.</p>	This element is used to mark each paragraph. It may contain multiple such links separated by a space, if the paragraph spans across multiple pages.
bold, spaced, italic, subscript, superscript	<hi>	<hi rend="bold:true;">bold text</hi>	@rend has five different values: "bold:true;", "italic:true;", "letterSpaced:true;", "superscript:true;", "subscript:true;"
music notation	<notatedMusic>	<notatedMusic rend="MEI">	The element contains a <desc>-Element with fixed content "MUSIK" so that it will be displayed in case of issues with rendering the MEI file, making it easier to look

		<pre> facts="#zone-id" source="zone-id.mei"> <desc>MUSIK</desc> </notatedMusic> </pre>	<p>for missing music notation in the frontend. With <code>@rend="MEI"</code> the frontend knows to treat this element and its contents differently than the other elements. More on that in the chapter on displaying music notations below. The <code>@source</code> contains a link to the file containing MEI-encoded music notation, named after the music notation's <code>zone-id</code>.</p>
graphics	<code><figure></code>	<pre> <figure facts="#zone-id"> <graphic url="zone-id.png"> </figure> </pre>	<p>Graphics from the text are captured as Portable Network Graphics (PNGs) and linked within the <code><figure></code> element as <code><graphic></code>. <code>@url</code> contains a link to the PNG file, named after the graphic's <code>zone-id</code>. <code>@rend="inline"</code> was used to differentiate between inline and block graphics. In rare cases of music notation not being transcribed but added as a graphic, those were marked with <code>@type="musicplaceholder"</code>.</p>
mathematical expressions	<code><formula></code>	<pre> <formula notation="tex">\$266 \frac{2}{3}\$</formula> </pre>	<p>Mathematical expressions are transcribed using LaTeX notation. This change in encoding style is marked by <code>@notation</code>.</p>
footnotes	<code><note></code>	<pre> <note facts="#zone-id" type="foot" n="*")>footnotetext</note> </pre>	<p>Footnotes are encoded as <code><note type="foot"></code>. The <code>@n</code> contains the characters used to reference the footnote in the text.</p>
lists	<code><list></code>	<pre> <list facts="#zone-id"><item>ite m1 text</item><item>item2 text</item></list> </pre>	<p>Lists are encoded as <code><list></code> with an <code><item></code>-element containing the text of each point on the list. The <code>@facts</code> contains a link to the <code><zone></code> of the corresponding text on the scanned page. It may contain multiple such links separated by a space, if the list spans across multiple pages or was divided into different zones during the transcription process.</p>
music-theoretical terms	<code><rs></code>	<pre> <rs ana="#concept_mus">Tongest altungen</rs> </pre>	<p>The <code><rs></code> element encodes parts of the text of special interest for the dualism debate. The <code>@ana</code> has one of the following values: <code>"#concept_mus"</code>, <code>"#concept_phy"</code>, <code>"#m_interval"</code>, <code>"#m_note"</code>, <code>"#m_chord"</code>, <code>"m_tonality"</code>.</p>

mentions of texts/works	<title>	<title ana="#text" ref="#W0042">Tonsetzkunst</title>	When texts and musical works are mentioned, their titles are encoded as <title ana="#text">. @ref is used to link to another XML file containing a list with all mentioned works together with further metadata: This XML file can be found here: https://github.com/fabianmoss/digimusth/blob/data/tei_logische-struktur/works.xml
mentions of authors	<persName>	<persName role="author" ref="#P0041">Weitzmann</persName>	When authors are mentioned, their names are encoded as <persName role="author">. @ref is used to link to another XML-file that contains a list with all mentioned authors together with further metadata. This XML-file can be found here: https://github.com/fabianmoss/digimusth/blob/data/tei_logische-struktur/people.xml
mentions of places	<placeName>	<placeName ref="#L0015">Frankfurt a. M.</placeName>	When places are mentioned, their names are encoded as <placeName>. @ref is used to link to another XML-file that contains a list with all mentioned locations together with further metadata. This XML-file can be found here: https://github.com/fabianmoss/digimusth/blob/data/tei_logische-struktur/locations.xml

2.6 Enhancing Data

Transcribing music notation

In the DDD project, an attempt was made to transcribe the music examples contained in the texts automatically with Optical Music Recognition (OMR), but that approach failed due to current limitations of these approaches, and the complexity and diversity of our source material (Moss et al., 2022a). It was thus decided to manually encode the examples using the widespread and simple Humdrum ****kern** format (Huron, 1997). While most examples could easily be encoded, some posed challenges because of graphical elements such as text, arrows and lines as well as analytical symbols combined with the music. Those were included as graphics. The corpus of encoded music examples is available on Zenodo (Moss et al., 2022b).

Transcribing Mathematical Expressions

Mathematical expressions and formulas were initially marked in the texts using the placeholder **\$\$\$MATH**. Replacing these required individual searching within the XML files and subsequent manual transcription of the corresponding expressions found in the source scans. This was initially attempted by transcribing the mathematical expressions using MathML (Caprotti & Carlisle, 1999). This XML-based language would have integrated directly with the TEI/MEI infrastructure. However, this approach proved to be difficult, error-prone, and most of all time-consuming because of MathML's inherent verbosity, which required the creation of long terms and complex, nested tag structures to define simple mathematical layouts. The following example, taken from HOS1879, illustrates the difference in complexity:

Scan:

wir nicht lieber gleich das d' als kl. Unterterz von f' , also
 $= 352 \times \frac{5}{6} = 293,3$ berechnet? Die endgiltige Antwort auf
diese Fragen kann allerdings erst dann gegeben werden, wenn
bereits von der Beschaffenheit und Construction unseres Tonsystems

MathML:

```
<formula notation="mathml">
  <m:math>
    <mo>=</mo>
    <mn>352</mn>
    <mo>&times;</mo>
    <mfrac>
      <mn>5</mn>
      <mn>6</mn>
    </mfrac>
    <mo>=</mo>
    <mn>293,3</mn>
  </m:math>
</formula>
```

In a second attempt, we chose to transcribe the expressions in LaTeX.¹² This proved to be faster, easier to apply, and less prone to error. The more concise LaTeX syntax reduced transcription time. Furthermore, LaTeX expressions could be converted into MathML in the future, should the need ever arise, ensuring compatibility with the TEI/MEI infrastructure. Each expression was transcribed using the **<formula>**

¹² <https://www.latex-project.org/>

element with the attribute `@notation="tex"`. Beginnings and endings of a formula were marked with the dollar signs (\$), following the standard LaTeX inline mode convention, as seen in the example below.

LaTeX:

```
<formula notation="tex">=$ 352 \times \frac{5}{6} = 293,3$</formula>
```

Nevertheless, some complex cases still required careful consideration and consultation, such as the following example from OET1866:

Diese Unterschiede sind in den Tabellen dadurch anschaulich gemacht worden, dass allemal die Hauptklänge eines Systemes, durch einen fetteren Strich ausgezeichnet wurden, so z. B. Tab A sub 4

$$\frac{c - \bar{e} - \underline{g}}{\times} = c^+ \text{ Hauptaccord in ton. } c$$

$$\frac{\bar{f} - \underline{as} - c}{\times} = c^0 \text{ Nebenaccord in ton. } \underline{as}$$

$$\frac{\bar{e} - \underline{g} - \bar{h}}{\times} = \bar{h}^0 \text{ Nebenaccord in ton. } c$$

dagegen auf Tab. C sub 4:

$$\frac{\bar{a} - c - \bar{e}}{\times} = \bar{e}^0 \text{ Nebenaccord in ton. } c$$

$$\frac{\bar{e} - \underline{gis} - \bar{h}}{\times} = \bar{e}^+ \text{ Nebenaccord in phon. } \underline{gis}$$

und sub 2;

$$\frac{\bar{f} - \bar{a} - c}{\times} = f^+ \text{ Hauptaccord in ton. } c$$

$$\frac{\bar{h} - \underline{des} - \bar{f}}{\times} = f^0 \text{ Hauptaccord in phon. } b$$

This example raised several questions: Which lines belong together? Should we transcribe it as separate mathematical expressions or a single one? How could we ensure that LaTeX expressions align with the rest of the text after the formula? Could we use a graphic instead of transcribing it? After clarifying that lines connected by an “x” belong together (these are dualistic pairs of triads), we considered transcribing it in LaTeX. However, the difficulty of aligning text and formulas in the web presentation resulted in the decision to integrate it as a graphic instead.

Transcribing Diagrams as SVG

Many of the texts contain elaborate diagrams depicting the relations between tones or chords, and semantically encoding them would be an interesting step for future work. Within the time constraints of the DigiMusTh project we could make a promising first step. A minimal example of a manual transcription of graphics as SVG and their inclusion into the TEI files as well as a minimal-publishing infrastructure can be found here on the GitHub repository of the Music Special Interest Group of the TEI.¹³

Adding graphics, tables and music notation as PNG

All zones marked as containing a graphic were extracted from the scanned page using a Python script¹⁴ so that parts of the texts that have not been transcribed can still be displayed online.

Some graphics were not assigned a dedicated zone if they were placed in the middle of a text line. Rather, these were marked by placeholders `$$GRAPHIC` and `$$MUSIC`, which had to be clipped from the scans manually before being linked in the text. The procedure was similar to the transformation of the

¹³ <https://github.com/TEI-Music-SIG/examples>; see also <https://tei-music-sig.github.io/>

¹⁴ https://github.com/fabianmoss/digimusth/blob/data/python/export_music_png.ipynb

mathematical expressions. We searched the placeholder positions in the scans and manually cropped the section with a snipping tool. The newly created images were saved in the corresponding folders based on their content type: graphic, music, or table. The files were named adhering to the naming pattern used for blocks of graphics and music encoding (e.g. `fac3_106_Graphic_1612545661783_1267_1.png`). This naming structure includes the `@fac3` identifier and the content type indicator (`_Graphic_`, `_Music_`, or `_Table_`). The extracted images could then be linked with the `<figure>` element. In the case of a musical graphic, the element `<figure>` was extended with the attribute `@type="musicplaceholder"`. Inline graphics were extended by the attribute `@rend="inline"`.

Transcribing overlines and underlines

In the DDD project, lines over or under tone names representing syntonic comma differences were encoded using curly braces as placeholders (`} }` for double overlines, `}` single overlines, `{ {` double underlines, `{` single underlines; see examples below). To replace them with the corresponding unicode character, we searched for those instances using the regular expression `(\\w)(\\w)(\\w)<\\hi>\\}` for three characters with double overline and replaced the findings with `$1 ¯ $2 ¯ $3 ¯ </hi>`. Resulting white space had to be removed manually. If a result had more than three characters we manually added missing overlines. The process was repeated for instances with two and one characters, respectively. For underlines, we adapted the same regular expression through `\\{\\{` or `\\{`. The example is taken from OET1866.

Scan

**zusammenfassen, wieder in einem neuen Systeme reiner
Quinten. Die grosse Terz von \bar{e} wäre hiernach \overline{gis} , und ana-
log die Unterterz von \underline{as} , — \underline{fcs} , die zugehörigen Quintensysteme**

Transcription

```
wäre hiernach <rs ana="#m_note"><hi rend="italic:true; fontSize:0.0; kerning:0;"> $\overline{gis}$ </hi></rs>,
```

While this procedure worked well for most texts, special cases arose in KRA1852 and THU1877. In the former, we could not define a fixed rule giving us all line instances. Instead of using the regex, we thus used a more general search for the curly brackets with the XPath expression `//text()[not(contains(., 'frac')) and not(parent::formula)]`. The XPath filtered out instances of curly braces in the formula element. We manually inspected the results and changed the placeholder.

Scan

Grunde keine Quinte giebt) seiner Größe
der absteigenden \bar{c} f, und eben so das der
(d. i. die sogenannte große Terz, außer

Transcription

```
<lb fac3="#fac3_33_r2117" n="N004"/>Grunde keine <rs ana="#m_interval">Quinte</rs> giebt) seiner Grö  
<lb fac3="#fac3_33_r2118" n="N005"/>der absteigenden <rs ana="#m_interval"> $\bar{c}$  f</rs>, und eben so das  
<lb fac3="#fac3_33_r2119" n="N006"/>(d. i. die sogenannte <rs ana="#m_interval">große Terz</rs>, auß
```

In THU1877 (and KRA1852) we found instances of triple, quadruple and quintuple over- or low lines that could not be converted and therefore still contain the curly braces placeholders:

Scan

Transcription:

```
ing:0;">F</hi>{(((</rs> und die <rs ana="#concept_mus">Phonika</rs> <rs ana="#m_note"><hi rend="italic:true; fontSize:0.0; kerning:0;">h</hi>}})}</rs>
```

Adding normdata from GND and Wikidata

The named entities in the texts were linked either to the Gemeinsame Normdatei (GND)¹⁵ or Wikidata.¹⁶ For locations and people, we used the GND database. For works, we decided to use the Wikidata database as it refers to works as abstract entities rather than specific prints. The reconciliation was done using OpenRefine (Miller, 2022).¹⁷ In cases of multiple or no matches, they were reconciled manually. Some entities could not be matched due to either missing information or absence in the target database. Once the reconciliation was finalized, we proceeded to export the data as TSV or CSV files, and transformed each file (works, location, people) with customized Python scripts into XML files.¹⁸

2.7 Integrating the collection to existing databases

Apart from publishing the collection on our own GitHub repository and project website (see Section 1.3) we also added the texts to the external text collection of the *German Text Archive* (Deutsches Textarchiv, DTA)¹⁹ in order to achieve a wider visibility as well as benefit from the automatic integration into related tools and services, such as Voyant, DWDS Search and also Text+ Federated Content Search.²⁰ To achieve integration, we transformed our texts to the data model of the DTA base format (DTABf), using a custom XSLT script.²¹

<pre><p facs="#facs_5_TextRegion_1626023279530_166"> <lb facs="#facs_5_r118" n="N001"/>Die Hoffnung <persName rol <lb facs="#facs_5_r119" n="N002"/>schweren Kämpfen, „die Aufi <lb facs="#facs_5_r1110" n="N003"/><rs ana="#concept_mus">Du <lb facs="#facs_5_r1111" n="N004"/>ganz ausgemerzt und an die <lb facs="#facs_5_r1112" n="N005"/>klanges</rs> nach seinem t <lb facs="#facs_5_r1113" n="N006"/>getreten sein wird“ („<ti <lb facs="#facs_5_r1114" n="N007"/>nicht; und wenn im Folgen <lb facs="#facs_5_r1115" n="N008"/><persName role="author" r <lb facs="#facs_5_r1116" n="N009"/>aus äusserlichen, praktisi <lb facs="#facs_5_r1117" n="N010"/>wahrung gegen eine Anerker <lb facs="#facs_5_r1118" n="N011"/>tigung der <rs ana="#conce <lb facs="#facs_5_r1119" n="N012"/>§ 17). </p></pre>	<pre><p> <lb n="N001"/>Die Hoffnung <persName><hi rendition="#g">Riem <lb n="N002"/>schweren Kämpfen, „die Auffassung des Mollaccor <lb n="N003"/>Dursinne (eine Frucht des Generalbasses) aus de <lb n="N004"/>ganz ausgemerzt und an die Stelle der Benennung <lb n="N005"/>klanges nach seinem tiefsten die nach seinem hä <lb n="N006"/>getreten sein wird“ („“, S. XIII) theile ich du <lb n="N007"/>nicht; und wenn im Folgenden die Terminologie u <lb n="N008"/><persName>v. <hi rendition="#g">Oettingen</hi> <lb n="N009"/>aus äusserlichen, praktischen Motiven, unter au <lb n="N010"/>wahrung gegen eine Anerkennung der principiell <lb n="N011"/>tigung der Tonicität und Phonicität (vgl. im Fc <lb n="N012"/>§ 17). </p></pre>
<p>Our own TEI data model.</p>	<p>The DTABf data model.</p>

¹⁵ https://gnd.network/Webs/gnd/DE/Home/home_node.html

¹⁶ https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page

¹⁷ <https://openrefine.org/>

¹⁸ <https://github.com/fabianmoss/digimusth/blob/data/python/convertcsv-to-tei.py>,

https://github.com/fabianmoss/digimusth/blob/data/python/csv-to-tei_works.py,

https://github.com/fabianmoss/digimusth/blob/data/python/csv-to-tei_location.py

¹⁹ <https://www.deutschestextarchiv.de/>

²⁰ <https://voyant-tools.org/>; <https://www.dwds.de/>; <https://fcs.text-plus.org/>

²¹ <https://github.com/fabianmoss/digimusth/blob/data/xslt/teizdtabf.xsl>

3 Website – publishing a digital edition online with minimal technical requirements

3.1 Tech Stack

The project website is hosted via GitHub Pages²² on a dedicated branch called “page”,²³ built with the static site generator Jekyll²⁴ and the Ed theme²⁵ that is particularly suited for minimal digital scholarly editions. For better organization we decided to additionally store all data on a separate “data” branch.²⁶ In order to display the tests on the web, the TEI XML needs to be transformed to static HTML pages, which was done using the JavaScript library CETElcean (Viglianti & del Rio Grande, 2025).²⁷ The MEI-encoded music examples were displayed using JavaScript library Verovio (Pugin, 2014).²⁸ As described above, mathematical expressions were transcribed using LaTeX and displayed with the help of JavaScript library MathJax. (Cervone, 2012).²⁹ We now describe the detailed procedures.

3.2 Displaying the texts online

Highlighted words

Two types of textual emphasis need to be distinguished: the first concerns text styles found in the printed editions of the texts, such as spaced, bold, or italic, as well as superscript or subscript types. The example below, taken from KUN1862, p. 8, illustrates the kinds of textual variation found in our source material and how it is displayed on our project website:

Der „Kritischen Beleuchtung“ ist am Schlusse auch noch von uns eine Beurtheilung des, auf das „Harmoniesystem“ Weitzmann's beziehlichen Schriftchens: „Die neue Harmonielehre im Streit mit der alten“ von demselben Verfasser als „Nachtrag“ beigefügt. —

Frankfurt a. M., im Herbst 1862.

Der „Kritischen Beleuchtung“ ist am Schlusse auch noch von uns eine Beurtheilung des, auf das „Harmoniesystem“ Weitzmann's beziehlichen Schriftchens: „Die neue Harmonielehre im Streit mit der alten“ von demselben Verfasser als „Nachtrag“ beigefügt. —

Frankfurt a. M., im Herbst 1862. F. J. Kunkel.

Secondly, terms marked up by the DigiMusTh project (e.g., named entities) come in multiple classes. “Authors” and “works” were annotated with a specific ID by the previous DDD project. The class of “concepts” contains two subclasses, namely “musical” and “physical”. The third class consists of terms that can be marked as musical intervals, notes, chords or tonalities. Lastly, there is the class of dates and locations. To distinguish their display from in-text styling, we opted for the use of background colors. To

²² <https://docs.github.com/en/pages>

²³ <https://github.com/fabianmoss/digimusth/tree/page>

²⁴ <https://jekyllrb.com/>

²⁵ <https://minicomp.github.io/ed/>

²⁶ <https://github.com/fabianmoss/digimusth/tree/data>

²⁷ <https://github.com/TEIC/CETElcean>

²⁸ <https://www.verovio.org/index.xhtml>

²⁹ <https://www.mathjax.org/>

optimize legibility for vision-impaired readers, we generated colors with the help of an online tool.³⁰ The following table shows the categories with their colors and associated HTML color codes (hexcode).

authors and works ■ #f2b8cf	concepts ■ #b8f2bb
music ■ #B3D6D0	locations and times ■ #ffb396

If terms were labeled with multiple classes the background color gets overwritten. There is no specific order of importance as none has been determined in the previous project (see the example from CAP1905, p. 8).

Teil I, S. 14: „Durch unsere Experimente sind wir induktiv zu einem einheitlichen Gesichtspunkt vorgedrungen, indem wir die Identität des Kombinationstones mit dem Grundbass der den primären Klang enthaltenden (verkürzten) Obertonreihe nachgewiesen haben. „Sowie der Grundton das Intervall bestimmt, bestimmt auch das Intervall den Grundton; es gibt im C-Klange nur eine grosse Terz c—e, gleichwie es für die grosse Terz c—e nur einen Grundton C gibt“ (Polak „Zeiteinheit“ (1900) S. 56, s. auch S. 16 Anm.)*

Coordinating footnotes

In the initial data collection process, footnotes were simply placed at the bottom of the respective page. After converting to TEI following a logical structure, the footnotes were manually tagged and placed in the running text. To visually differentiate between these text types, we chose to display footnotes to the right of the running text as floating divs. This approach led to some difficulties since, in some texts, footnotes contain music, graphics, or their own footnotes. These elements are then much smaller than they would be in the running text. For the images and music examples we have added an on-click function to open the files in a new tab as bigger elements to allow a closer read (see [chapter below](#) for the implementation).

The implementation of the footnotes is dependent on Javascript. Firstly all notes are collected from the text. After applying a filter on the total number the @n attribute gets extracted. This marker is left behind in the main text and allows a user to click on it to be guided (through color highlighting and automatic scrolling) to the matching footnote.

It is especially challenging to calculate correct positions for the display of footnotes. As they should be aligned with the text line even when the page gets resized. This is reliant on the marker in the main text body as this determines the position. If there is already a footnote the new footnote is added below. This calculation needs to be done after all images and graphics have been loaded in the document. See below an example of HOS1879 (p. 5) of an unselected and a selected footnote:

Nicht anders, als mit der grossen, verhält es sich auch mit der kleinen Terz. So ist Somit erhalten wir zwischen der pythagoräischen und der natürlichen kleinen Terz abermals das vorige Verhältniss des Komma — doch umgekehrt; die erstere ist das kleinere, die letztere das grössere Intervall: Um diese wichtigen Unterschiede der pythagoräischen und natürlichen Intervalle auch in der Schrift anzudeuten, wurden verschiedene Mittel in Anwendung gebracht. Moritz Hauptmann *) bezeichnete die durch Quintenschritte gefundenen Terzen mit gleichen (grossen oder kleinen), die unmittelbar bestimmten mit verschiedenen Buchstaben: C—E oder e—e wäre also eine pythagoräische grosse, e—es oder C—Es eine ebensolche kleine Terz, C—e, e—E, C—es, e—Es wären natürliche Intervalle. A. v. Oettingen **) schlug die bequemere Bezeichnung der Kommaunterschiede durch horizontale, über oder unter dem Buchstaben anzubringende (von Hauptmann nur für ein Doppelkomma angewandte) Striche vor und Helmholtz stellte diese Schrift in der Weise fest, dass jeder über dem Buchstaben befindliche Strich die jenem entsprechende durch Quintenschritte gefundene Tonhöhe um ein Komma erhöht, jeder unter demselben angebrachte sie um ebensoviel erniedrigt. So ist denn

*) (Die Natur der Harmonik und Metrik. Von M. Hauptmann. 2. Aufl. Leipzig 1873.)

**) (Harmoniesystem in dualer Entwicklung. Von Dr. Arthur von Oettingen. Dorpat und Leipzig, 1866.)

As this logic extracts all footnotes, nested footnotes are processed twice, therefore showing up multiple times and disturbing the calculation of the positions. We chose to leave nested footnotes inside their

³⁰ <https://medialab.github.io/iwanthue/>

parent and format them in a smaller font size, which might also increase readability for users, as example see an extract form KUN1863 below:

jener Annahme noch mehr berechtigt. — Insbesondere ist die vom Verfasser als 4-Molltonleiter Nr. 1 aufgestellte Tonfolge keine neue Erfindung, denn die Entstehung und der erste Gebrauch dieser Leiter ist uralte, und die Physiognomie derselben orientalischen Gepräges. Es ist nämlich dieselbe, entweder die authentisch-phrygische, oder die (Hypo-äolische) Leiter, der man aber auch aufwärts fortzuschreiten gestattete ^{**}).

Könnte nun auch kein Kunstgenosse aus der alten Schule, welcher in das Wesen der Harmonieen gründlich eingedrungen, trotz der vielversprechenden pomphaften Ankündigung: „... musikalisch-theoretische Begründung der durch die neuesten Kunstschöpfungen bewirkten Umgestaltung und Weiterbildung der Harmonik“, und wiederum: „die Gesetze 2c. noch nicht erklärter Zusammenklänge und Accordfolgen zu ergründen 2c.“, — aus der Fassung gebracht und in den Traum einer glanzreichen musikalischen Morgenröthe eingehüllt werden, so dürfte aber jetzt nach genommener Einsicht der Weitzmann'schen Tonartensysteme auch mancher noch im Schwanken gewesener Musiker alten Schlages, ob nicht dennoch ein Einführen in unbekannte musikalische Gefilde und Fluren möglich, vollkommen enttäuscht sein, da er ja augenfällig in den aufgestellten Leitern — abgesehen von der noch vorenthalteneren näheren Anweisung für den melodischen Verbrauch derselben — die Möglichkeit einer ihm fremden Accordgestaltung nach naturgemäßer Bildungsweise nicht erkennen kann. Ja nicht einmal der Erhöhung der 4. Leiterstufe in Moll wird in der Aufstellung dieser Tonartensysteme und Leitern gedacht, wie in manchen älteren Lehrbüchern (Vogler, Portmann und andere), um die Accorde mit übermäßiger Sexte, wenn auch nicht als vollberechtigte Bürger, so doch als sehr willkommene Beisassen oder Permissionisten in die musikalische Harmonie-Gemeinde aufzunehmen.

Doch urtheilen wir nicht zu voreilig?

„Wie aber die weichere Durtonart hier den chromatischen Tonar benutzt, so kann eine jede Tonart außer ihren Stammtönen noch alle übrigen Töne unseres Tonsystems als chromatische Nebentöne in Anwendung bringen, um damit bald ihre Melodien aususchmücken, bald ihren Harmonieen ein reicheres Colorit zu geben.“

Als Durchgänge, Wechselnoten 2c. werden nach der alten Schule auch schon lange her die chromatischen — oder wie wir beziehlich zu irgend einer Tonart sprechen — leiterfremden Töne benutzt, in Folge dessen dann nicht nur melodische Verzierungen, sondern auch nicht selten chromatische Accorde entstehen. Wird aber ein Ton als wesentlicher Bestandtheil in eine Tonart und deren Tonleiter eingereiht, wie oben der Tonar in die „weichere Durtonleiter“ der 6. Stufe von C, dann würde dieser Ton auch in seine Gerechtsame als selbstständiges Glied der verschiedenen Grundharmonieen eintreten, und es müßte derselbe z. B. in dieser, der C-Durleiter, als Bestandtheil der Grunddreiklänge von *d - F - as* —, *f - as - c* — und *as - c - e*, der Vierklänge 2c. vorerst nicht zu gedenken, angesehen werden und nicht bloß für den melodischen Schmuck und des harmonischen Colorits da sein. Räumt nun der Verfasser „allen übrigen Tönen unseres Tonsystems“ gleiches Recht ein, wie hier dem Tönear, so müßte dann auch jeder dieser Töne, je nach seiner Stellung in der Tonreihe, ebenfalls als selbstständiges Glied verschiedener Grundharmonieen seine Berechtigung haben. Daß eine solche Theorie in's Bodenlose führte, ist leicht ersichtlich. Nach solchen Principien wäre es aber dann auch unnöthig gewesen, sich mit den verschiedenen Tonartensystemen zu befassen und daraus wieder eben so viele verschiedene siebenstönige Tonleitern zu deduciren; viel einfacher, neu und gewiß auch genial wäre es, ein für allemal die zwölfstönige chromatische Tonreihe, oder auch die enharmonische mit ihren 17 Noten, oder gar endlich das ganze Regiment der oben für's „Tonsystem“ aufgestellten Fünfunddreißig, so eine wahrhaftige Universaltonleiter, als Grundlage leitereigener Accorde und „mächtig hervortretender“, melodischer und harmonischer Tongebilde ganz uneingeschränkt zur Verfügung zu stellen! —

** (Man sehe hierüber die betreffenden Abhandlungen in älteren Lehrbüchern, z. B. Fink's „Musikalische Grammatik“, 30. Kap.; André's „Lehrbuch der Tonsetzkunst“, 1. Band, 19. Kap.; „Kompositionslehre“ von Marx, 1. Band, 2. Buch, 2. Abtheilung; „Versuch einer geordneten Theorie der Tonsetzkunst“ von G. Weber (†) Unseres Wissens war es dieser in mehrfacher Beziehung thatsächliche Reformator in unserer Musiktheorie (— womit wir jedoch keineswegs alle seine aufgestellten Lehrsätze vertheidigen und seinen ausgesprochenen Ansichten blindlings huldigen wollen —), der schon im Jahre 1811 in den „Heidelberger Jahrbüchern“ und später in seinem vorbezeichneten Werke eine auf- und absteigend gleichförmige Molltonleiter als Grundlage zur Bildung sämtlicher leitereigenen Harmonieen aufstellte. Er bezeichnete dieselbe mit „wesentlicher“ Form zum Unterschiede von der „herkömmlichen“, wie er die ältere Form nannte; Fink scheidet die beiden Formen durch „harmonische“ und „melodische“ Ordnung, jedoch uneigentlich und nicht genügend begründet, da die Töne beider Formen stufen- und sprunghaft melodisch, und ebenso — mit Ausnahme jener der erhöhten 6. und erniedrigten 7. Stufe in der herkömmlichen Form — auch harmonisch zu leitereigenen Grundaccorden, verwendet werden; nennt sie „historische“ Form. —), Band IV, Anhang Seite 150 (3. Auflage.) —

Rendering music notation

To display music on our webpage we decided to use Verovio (Pugin et al., 2014). The basic implementation to display MEI files as Scalable Vector Graphics (SVG) is straightforward. However, in our case many examples were cut off as the size and scope of examples varies greatly: some spanning multiple pages while others only showcase a few notes. Therefore we needed a dynamic execution dependent on the specific files. In the first step all occurrences of notated music are collected.

```
const musicElements =
    document.querySelectorAll('tei-notatedmusic[rend="MEI"]');
```

Out of each node the @source attribute is then extracted that stores the filename. After building the path to the MEI file, the file is loaded, analyzed, and—depending on the number of pages—height and scale are adjusted.

```
vrvToolkit.loadData(data);
const pageCount = vrvToolkit.getPageCount();
let scale = 80;
let pageHeight = 12000;

// Adjust scale/pageHeight for readability
```

```
if (pageCount === 1) {
  scale = 80;
  pageHeight = 6000;
} else if (pageCount <= 3) {
  scale = 100;
  pageHeight = 12000;
} else {
  scale = 120;
  pageHeight = 20000;
}

vrvToolkit.setOptions({
  adjustPageHeight: true,
  breaks: "auto",
  pageWidth: 2100,
  pageHeight,
  scale
});
```

The SVG is then rendered and Verovio produces an inner and an outer SVG that influence the sizing and need to be taken into consideration for the display.

```
const svg = vrvToolkit.renderToSVG(pageNum, {});
```

When no MEI file can be found the code automatically falls back to display the PNG version. Therefore, naming needs to be exact and the folder structure needs to follow the pre-determined pattern. For users to be able to display the musical examples on a larger scale we added a function that opens the data in a new tab. Since the music is generated as SVG rather than simply loaded in, this data is stored in a blob.³¹

Displaying Mathematical Expressions

Mathematical expressions are rendered using MathJax with some minor adjustments in the configuration (see code below). We changed characters marking the beginning and end of a formula, allowing the \$ symbol as tag. Further, we disabled the built-in MathJax right-click menu and chose not to load this library over a Content Delivery Network, but save the data locally.

```
MathJax = {
  tex: {
    inlineMath: { '[+]' : [['$', '$']] } // adding the $ as a marker for
    formulas
  },
  options: {
    enableMenu: false // disables the context menu
  }
};
```

Additionally, the script checks for mathematical expressions as they are loaded onto the page.

```
if (window.MathJax) {
  // Tell MathJax to process newly inserted content
  MathJax.typesetPromise();
}
```

As there are some expressions that resemble mathematical fractions but that are actually figured-bass notation we chose to use CSS for visualization, e.g. KUN1863:

³¹ <https://wiki.selfhtml.org/wiki/JavaScript/Blob>

<lb facs="#facs_57_line_1614708594662_928" n="N003"/>dann in den durch zwei <rs ana="#concept_mus">Vorhalte</rs> <rs ana="#concept_mus">verzögerten</rs> <rs ana="#m_chord"><hi rend="italic:true; fontSize:0.0; kerning:0;">G</hi>-dur-Dreiklang</rs> (in der <rs ana="#concept_mus"><rs ana="terzsextlage">63-Lage</rs></rs>) auf. Das <hi rend="italic:true; fontSize:0.0; kerning:0;"><rs ana="#m_note">h</rs></hi> des <rs ana="#concept_mus">Basses</rs> bleibt

Trugfortschrittung in den Sekundenaccord nimmt und dieser löst sich sodann in den durch zwei Vorhalte verzögerten G-dur-Dreiklang (in der $\frac{6}{3}$ -Lage) auf. Das *b* des Basses bleibt nun als Halteton liegen, über welchem der *b*-moll-Dreiklang und sodann der verminderte Dreiklang *fis ac* erscheint, der endlich regelmäßig in den G-dur-Dreiklang übergeht:

Displaying Graphics

Other images that are saved as Portable Network Graphics (PNGs) are either loaded as image blocks (centered horizontally in the text) or inline. In the latter case, they are rendered with a maximum height of 3em. These are usually single symbols or text in a foreign language, mostly Greek (see CAP1905, p. 9 below).

7. Der Mollklang, z. B. a c e (kurz notiert A₀, während ein alleinstehendes A den Durklang anzeigt) ist je nach dem tonalen Zusammenhänge zu erklären als A \natural cis e, also als alterierter („getrübt“) Durdreiklang mit dem Grundton

a, oder aber als $\underbrace{A C e}_{(g)}$, also als Doppelklang mit den Grundtönen a („Basis“) und e (durch diese Grundtonqualität gewinnt das c das Übergewicht über die schwächere Basisterz cis). Weiter kann der Molldreiklang a c e

auch verstanden werden als $\underbrace{(F) a C e}_{(g)}$, also als Doppelklang mit den Grundtönen f und c, oder endlich als

As images might be hard to read due to their size or position we added an `onClick` function that opens an image in a new tab. Since we have fallback images, images in footnotes, and regular images we need this functionally to work on multiple elements and therefore be included at different positions of the code. See below the code to add the function onto the SVGs and the images.

```
const svgString = new XMLSerializer().serializeToString(svgClone);
// Create a blob and open in new tab -> blob needed because svg gets
// generated and isnt saved as such
const blob = new Blob([svgString], { type: 'image/svg+xml' });
const url = URL.createObjectURL(blob);
window.open(url, '_blank');
```

Code for images:

```
// Create a link wrapper so the image is clickable
const link = document.createElement("a");
link.href = pngPath;
link.target = "_blank"; // open in a new tab
link.appendChild(img);
```

```
// Replace the node contents with the clickable fallback image
```

```
node.innerHTML = "";  
node.appendChild(link);
```

Displaying page numbers and linking to facsimiles

In the footer we added a button on the left-hand side displaying the current physical page number. Clicking on it opens the scan in a new window. For this we extract the <pb> elements. However, sometimes there is no value assigned to the @n attribute of a <pb> element, which can distort the ordering of displayed numbers. In OET1866 for example, the <fac> element with the number 42 can be found on the physical page with the number 34, which as a digital scan in JPG format has the number 51. We recommend citing using the facs element.

 See facsimile of page 33

Table of contents

To navigate within the texts we use fist-level headings and implement them through a combination of the already existing structure in Ed and CETEIcean. Ed automatically adds a table of contents (toc) in the navigation bar. If the text is loaded from this markdown file the template automatically adds IDs to the text where headings are defined. It is therefore important that the spellings of headings in the text and the toc element are identical. To add the ID the anchor jumps to in our through XML loaded text we use a CETEIcean behaviour (see code below) that adds a <div> element in front of head elements with an ID. This ID is generated from the text in the head, therefore following the predetermined Ed logic. Further this structure technically allows the user to jump to all possible <head> elements. Due to a high number of subtitles we chose to only add fist-level heads.

```
"head": function (elt) {  
  // Clone the element and move it into a div  
  let clone = document.createElement("div");  
  
  // Copy over the inner HTML so the TEI content displays  
  clone.innerHTML = elt.innerHTML;  
  
  // Find the first <hi> in the clone  
  let hi = clone.querySelector("tei-hi");  
  if (hi) {  
    // Extract and clean up its text, following the ed logic  
    let text = hi.textContent.trim();  
    let cleaned = text  
      .replace(/[\.,\/#!$%^&\*;\{\}=\_`~()?''"'""'"',']/g, "")  
      .replace(/\s+/g, "-")  
      .toLowerCase();  
  
    // Add the id attribute  
    clone.setAttribute("id", cleaned);  
  }  
  
  // Return the new HTML structure so CETEIcean renders it  
  return clone;  
},
```

3.3 Indices

In the texts terms have been annotated into various categories. While authors and works were already equipped with IDs, all the other classes were not. In the course of this project we developed a script to add

IDs to categories and chose to apply it on the locations since the number of occurrences is still manageable, for the concepts the occurrences are in the thousands and normalizing them was outside of a reasonable scope. Therefore the webpage offers three index pages, which presents users the occurrences in context and allows users to jump to the text extract to read more.

From a technical standpoint, the indices are saved as XML files, following TEI conventions. These files are then loaded onto the page using JavaScript, an extension of these files therefore automatically updates the data on the online site. In the base view the user sees an alphabetically sorted list of the entities, a click on an entity opens a new page. This page displays the external norm database identifier, as well as notes connected to the entity. Further the occurrences of the entity is seen in context for all texts in the collection and through a link, the user can jump to the highlighted occurrence in the fulltext. The works can be found in their own index, but if they could be connected to an author, they can also be found in the people index.

Johann Sebastian Bach

GND: 4226038-3

Georg Capellen: *Die Zukunft der Musiktheorie* (1905) ↗

...Molldreiklanges vollzogen. Noch bei **Bach** finden wir Mollstücke häufig... [View full ↗](#)

...Blut und Wunden“ in **Bachs** Matthäus- Passion als vorzüglich für... [View full ↗](#)

Moritz Hauptmann: *Die Natur der Harmonik und der Metrik: Zur Theorie der Musik* (1853) ↗

...Volkslied und in der **Bach'schen** Fuge, oder BeethovenschenSymphonie. Wenn... [View full ↗](#)

Otakar Hostinský: *Die Lehre von den musikalischen Klängen: ein Beitrag zur aesthetischen Begründung der Harmonielehre* (1879) ↗

...langjährige Praxis festgestellten, seit **Bach** und Beethoven aber zu... [View full ↗](#)

Franz Joseph Kunkel: *Kritische Beleuchtung des C. F. Weitzmann'schen Harmoniesystems*. (1863) ↗

...hervorhebt, indem er hierzu **Bach**, Haydn, Mozart und Beethoven... [View full ↗](#)

...Compositionen unserer größten Tonmeister, **Bach** und Mozart, ganzstufig und... [View full ↗](#)

...Abth. I mitgetheilt, schon **Bach**, Haydn, Mozart und Beethoven... [View full ↗](#)

3.4 Search

The Ed template comes with an already configured search based on the elasticlunr implementation³² by Kathie Decora, which we have adapted for our project, as well as the lunr languages script³³ by Mihai Valentin and the lunr stemmer by Oleg Mazko. However this search tool is not usable out of the box.

Firstly the code expects the texts to be in the markdown files. For this project the text page is generated and various sources are loaded in, therefore the text content is in the XML files. To be able to use the search we have chosen to build the index manually and place it in the markdown files. When this initial search has found a string in the index, the full text then is searched to find the string in context. While this approach may seem overkill for our small collection it might come in handy when a lot of texts have been added.

³² <http://katydecorah.com/code/lunr-and-jekyll/>

³³ <https://github.com/MihaiValentin/lunr-languages>

Secondly the template initially could not handle German texts therefore we updated the code with a version that can support German. For example, when searching for “Piano,” several results are shown. Below you see the search interface and an excerpt of the result in KRA1852 that is also reachable via a direct link.³⁴

Search

The search function allows users to look for a specific term or partial word matches within the corpus. The corpus refers exclusively to the textual data of this project.

The screenshot shows a search interface with a search bar containing the word "Piano". Below the search bar, a green button indicates "Found in 5 texts". A list of search results is displayed, each with a green triangle icon and a snippet of text. The first result is by Franz Joseph Kunkel, the second by Otto Kraushaar, and the third by Adolf Thürlings. The snippet for Otto Kraushaar contains the word "Piano" highlighted in yellow. Below the list, there are two more results with downward-pointing triangles, indicating they are collapsed.

Wenn das gleichzeitige Erfassen von Tönen den nämlichen räumlichen Bedingungen, wie das von sichtbaren Dingen unterworfen wäre, so müßten sich die im sogenannten Tonraume, nämlich nach Höhe und Tiefe einander zunächst liegenden Töne, namentlich die Bestandtheile der chromatischen Tonleiter im Zusammenklang auffassen lassen. Dies ist aber unmöglich, wie ein Versuch auf dem **Piano**forte zu erweisen vermag, und führt sonach zu dem Schluß, daß die Töne der kleinsten

When a term is found in the static index, the entire XML file is searched for its occurrences. These are then shown in context and a user can click on it to be guided to the actual text.

3.5 Whitespace issues

The initial digital data was encoded true to the physical book including line breaks. However a presentation on a webpage allows multiple formats and users to view the page on diverse devices. The reading experience should be pleasant for all. During this project we had various issues with whitespaces: either missing whitespaces, leading to words being glued together, or too many whitespaces, ripping words apart. During close analysis different cases could be identified and fixed accordingly. A common cause could be found in missing white spaces between certain tags, this was fixed using various regular expressions that systematically added whitespace between the identified tags.

A main issue were lines ending in a punctuation character element (<pc>) that led to inserted whitespaces. Punctuation marks are not displayed online and controlled via CSS rules. However if a whitespace character appeared it was fixed using CETElcean behaviour. While it was important to remove the linebreak display in the fulltext, for some parts, such as lists, line breaks are very important for the semantics of the text. See for example NAU1858, p. 14:

³⁴

https://fabianmoss.github.io/digimusth/texts/KRA1852/?q=Piano#fac=%23fac_18_TextRegion_1632819230547_899

Bezeichnet man die relative Schwingungszahl der Quinte mit Q und die der grossen Terz mit T , so ist allgemeiner Ausdruck für die relative Schwingungszahl eines Tones

$$\text{der 1}^{\text{ten}} \text{ Classe} = Q^n \cdot 2^x$$

$$\text{der 2}^{\text{ten}} \text{ Classe} = T \cdot Q^n \cdot 2^x$$

$$\text{der 3}^{\text{ten}} \text{ Classe} = \frac{Q^n \cdot 2^x}{T}$$

3.6 Adding texts to the collection

All following steps have to be done on the “page” branch³⁵ for a new text to appear on the webpage. In order to add a text to the collection, a markdown file must be created for it, containing specific information, which is reused at certain points in the code. It must contain the following structure:

- layout: music
- title
- author
- name
- year
- search
- (optional toc)

An example would be:

```
---
layout: music
title: Die neue Harmonielehre im Streit mit der alten
author: Carl Friedrich Weitzmann
name: WEI1861
year: 1861
search: abgedruckt, abgegrenztes, abhandlung, abschlusse, ... übrigens
---
```

The `layout: music` key-value pair must be kept, since it contains all functions needed to display the music data and correctly load the XMLs. The table of content can be extracted using a custom Jupyter notebook,³⁶ and a script automatically adds IDs to the elements marked as head in the text. As the strings must match for the logic to work we advise not to do this manually. Here is an example for RIE1905:

```
toc:
- I. Einleitung.
- II. Sind die Obertöne der „Grund“ der Konsonanz?
- III. Intervallverschmelzung oder Klangvertretung?
- IV. Die wahre Wurzel des harmonischen Dualismus.
- V. Das Grundton-Problem.
```

For the static search we need to have the content words in the markdown as the pages are generated from the XML files. You can use another custom notebook³⁷ to extract unique words from XML files and then add them to the specific markdown file. Both scripts are found in the data branch. The markdown file then is placed in the `_texts` folder, while a folder named after the text’s ID is placed in `data`, following the structure in the following image:

³⁵ <https://github.com/fabianmoss/digimusth/tree/page>

³⁶ https://github.com/fabianmoss/digimusth/blob/data/python/extract_heads.ipynb

³⁷ https://github.com/fabianmoss/digimusth/blob/data/python/extract_searchterms.ipynb

The MEI files are placed in `data`, and their fallback PNG images in `music`, while all other images are deposited in `graphic`. Facsimiles are found in `scans`. Some texts have an additional folder called `table` which contains PNG images of tables. When a text is added this way, it will automatically show up in the overview of the texts and will be searched through.

Once you have followed all the steps open a pull request which can be merged after a review by the repository's owner.

4 Dissemination – communicating project outcomes to the scholarly community

The progress and the outcomes of the DigiMusTh project have been presented at various occasions in order to obtain feedback from the scholarly community and to disseminate our results. While the project focused on a particular collection of texts—19th century German music theory treatises—, we believe that many of its aspects, such as the multimodal nature of the documents with text, music, tabular, and mathematical elements, as well as our decision to work within a minimal editing framework based on static rendering of the website can be adapted for many other scenarios in the digital humanities.

4.1 Academic conferences

TEI/MEC conference 2023

At the joint conference of the Text Encoding Initiative and the Music Encoding Initiative in 2023 in Paderborn, Germany, we presented preliminary work on text-music interlinking, which played an essential role in this project. The feedback obtained at the conference was instrumental in preparing the proposal.

1. Roeder, T., Köster, M., & Moss, F. C. (2023). Music-Text Interlinking as a Challenge for Digital Encodings of Music-Theoretical Writings. *Encoding Cultures – Joint MEC and TEI Conference 2023*, 4–8 September 2023, Zentrum Musik – Edition – Medien (ZenMEM), Paderborn, Germany. <https://teimec2023.uni-paderborn.de/contributions/124.html>

MEC conference 2025

During the [Music Encoding Conference 2025](#) in London (from June 3rd to June 6th) the preliminary studies and the current status of the project have been presented (“A Minimal Publishing Model for Text and Music Notation”). Minimal examples are available on the TEI Music SIG website: github.com/TEI-Music-SIG/examples

2. Stickler, F., Roeder, T., & Moss, F. C. (2025) A Minimal Publishing Model for Text and Music Notation. *Music Encoding Conference 2025*. 3–6 June 2025, London, UK.

TEI conference 2025

During the [Text Encoding Initiative Conference 2025](#) in London (from September 16th to September 20th) the current status of the project was presented (“Multimodality and Minimal Publishing: TEI, MEI and more in 19th-Century Music Treatises”). Expanded minimal examples are available on the TEI Music SIG website: github.com/TEI-Music-SIG/examples

3. Roeder, T., Klinger, J., Stickler, F., Keupp, C., & Moss, F. C. (2025) Multimodality and Minimal Publishing: TEI, MEI and more in 19th-Century Music Treatises. *25th Annual Meeting of the Text Encoding Initiative*. 16–17 September 2025, Kraków, Poland. <https://10.5281/zenodo.17205769>

4.2 Invited talks and presentations

Coffee Talks at ZPD

On Wednesday 21st of May 2025 Felicitas Stickler presented her work to colleagues at the Centre for Philology and Digitality in Würzburg. The presentation focused on her Bachelor thesis and a project realized during her studies. Following an insightful talk, she responded to questions from an engaged audience.

4. Stickler, F. (2025). *Coffee Talks at ZPD*, Würzburg, Germany.

Text+ Kooperationsprojekte

Fabian Moss introduced this project on the 28th of May 2025 during a meeting of all current Text+ projects in the field of organizing collections.

5. Moss, F. C. (2025, May 23) Vorstellung Kooperationsprojekt “Aufbau einer offenen digitalen Sammlung historischer musiktheoretischer Texte aus dem deutschsprachigen Raum anhand von Beispielen aus dem 19. Jahrhundert (DigiMusTh)”. *14. Gesamttreffen TA Collections Text+*, online.

DH Kolloquium der BBAW

6. Moss, F. C. (2025, June 30). Text+ Musik: Multimodale Kodierungsherausforderungen im DigiMusTh-Kooperationsprojekt. *DH-Kolloquium an der Berlin-Brandenburgischen Akademie der Wissenschaften*, online.

Abschlussevent Text+-Kooperationsprojekte von 2025

7. Moss, F. C. & Roeder, T. (2026, February 17). DigiMusTh: Aufbau einer offenen digitalen Sammlung historischer musiktheoretischer Texte aus dem deutschsprachigen Raum anhand von Beispielen aus dem 19. Jahrhundert. *Abschlussevent Text+-Kooperationsprojekte von 2025*, online.

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